

Reading Across Languages: An Exploratory Study of L1 and L2 Combined Comprehension

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Abstract

Reading is a skill shared by all living things, including animals and humans. Animals read other animals and humans by using their senses of smell, taste, and so on to determine whom they can and cannot trust. Humans, whether they can or not. When a child reads in a second language, the child typically brings with her a wealth of knowledge, including world and word knowledge, metacognitive and metalinguistic knowledge, strategies, processes, and prior literacy experiences from her first language (L1 hereafter). In other words, second-language or L2 reading has access to a variety of additional resources, including the L1. Reading ability in the first language must be valued as a rich resource repertoire that can be used to enable reading comprehension in a second language. If these resources aren't used. It's like asking children to keep their languages in two different parts of their brains. Based on these above observations, a study was conducted to assess the efficacy of bilingual teaching among Arabic-speaking learners.

Keywords: Reading, Arabic Language, English, Classroom, Bilingual, ESL

Literate people read in the traditional sense of the word; they decipher signs, symbols, and texts to derive meaning and, as a result, acquire knowledge. Those who have never attended school may not be able to read in this sense, but they can 'read' people's faces, minds, and weather by decoding facial expressions and gestures, cloud movement, and so on. If learned, such reading of people's gestures, body language, or nature is done through observation or, if taught, through incidental and indirect suggestions made by caregivers. In this sense, all humans are capable and efficient readers. Different cultures, however, interpret gestures differently, so when humans travel to other places, particularly countries, they must relearn to read and 'interpret' body language in new ways. This learning, on the other hand, does not occur in a vacuum, and no such traveler begins from scratch. Previous knowledge is compared to previous experiences; the more exposure, the faster learning, and adaptation.

Reading the printed word is similar to but not the same as this other sense of the verb "to read." While there are cultural differences, and texts are organized differently on different continents. If the languages are the same, there are very few differences. Texts written by people from various continents can also be read easily. However, when humans read texts in two or more languages. It cannot be assumed that their capabilities are all the same. They may have to relearn to read (for example, when the script changes from orthographic to ideographic) or adapt their existing reading abilities to accommodate new scripts. This is a common occurrence, but anyone who has learned (or acquired) two or more languages and is literate in all of them is likely to use his ability or proficiency in one language to help him understand texts in the other. This is analogous to using knowledge of gestures from one culture to compare and contrast and thus interpret gestures from another.

However, this adaptation or utilization of available capability does not appear to be an inherent part of language education in multilingual classrooms. This thesis contends that teaching all second or foreign languages in general, and reading ability in particular, must be able to capitalize on existing abilities. If this is not done, it is equivalent to viewing the mind as a blank slate. Even in a first language, reading requires complex cognitive skills to interpret the text into something meaningful. It is multidimensional, specialized, and complex, requiring a variety of general skills. These include psychomotor skills, cognitive abilities, and working memory. When it comes to reading in a second language, this complexity multiplies due to linguistic differences (linguistic distance) between the first and second languages, processing differences that emerge from reading in the second language, and language variations in different sociolinguistic contexts. When the two languages are bi-Scriptal, the complexity multiplies. Furthermore, the dual-language involvement of L2 reading necessitates constant interaction on the one hand and constant fine-tuning in order to accommodate the incongruent demands that each language brings on the other. Given the complexities of reading, it is truly remarkable that so many people have learned to read in a second or third language for a variety of reasons. When children are expected to have 'complex reading capability,' the reading process becomes much more complicated.

Teaching reading to bilingual children

Children must first be taught print awareness, which includes how to hold the book, print directionality (top to bottom and left to right), knowledge of spoken language, phonological awareness (the ability to break a word into individual sounds or vice versa), and symbol-sound relationship (the name-sound relationship of the writing system that represents sounds). When teaching children to read in a second language, they do not need to be "taught all over again" the print concepts of how to handle the book, how to recognize spaces between words to know where one begins and one ends, how a string of letters of the alphabet makes words, and how to decode and encode print. In this sense, one could argue that children who read in their second language have reading abilities. They do, however, require a new script to be taught to them, new grammatical links between words, new links between signifiers and the signified, irregularities in the sound-symbol relationship, etc. In order to enable meaningful and fruitful reading capability in a second or third language. The capability available in the first language must be used as a foundation or as a springboard. "Reading in a second language

(L2) is not a monolingual event," Upton and Lee-Thompson correctly state. "L2 readers have access to their first language (L1) as they read, and many use it as a strategy to help comprehend an L2 text" (2001: 469).

The goal of this study is to build on children's existing L1 reading skills and use them as a foundation to teach them to read in L2 with a focus on Tamil and English. The research will be conducted in regional (Tamilnadu) medium schools, with a focus on children who are mostly first-generation learners. The goal is to improve reading ability in L2, English, without neglecting the mother tongue. The position papers of the National Focus Group (2006) also ask teachers to use existing capabilities so that the children's L1 will strengthen their English learning. However, no clear framework for implementation is provided.

This research is regarded as one such experiment. It asks the following questions:

- What are children in Tamil Nadu's regional medium primary schools able to read in their L1 (Assamese) and L2 (English)?
- Do they use Tamil reading strategies in their first language?
- What exactly are these strategies?
- How can the strategies be communicated to the children?
- Can the strategies be transferred to their L2 (English) to aid in the development of comprehension skills?"

Reading comprehension is viewed in this research as a complex cognitive, interactive skill that requires the reader to create meaning by connecting the information in the text to their own prior knowledge. different words. According to research, the "integrative interaction of derived text information and pre-existing reader knowledge" is necessary for successful reading comprehension (Koda, 2005: 4).

According to research from Indian contexts (Kumar, 2011), writing in a second language is a bilingual activity, and writers who have access to more than one language can perform cognitive operations in either language while writing. This approach is fairly typical in L2 and serves a variety of functions, including idea generation planning and text organization. an analysis of the text that was produced. Think-aloud protocols have been used in many research studies conducted in Western contexts, and they have taught us a great deal about how to use L1 in L2 classrooms.

However, a large body of research contends that, for L2 and bilingual child populations, some skills do appear to transfer from the L1 to the L2, supporting some versions of the Interdependence Hypothesis. Evidence involving bilingual children's L1 and L2 reading skills reveals "moderately significant relationships" (Cummins, 1991; Verhoeven, 1990; 1994). According to Verhoeven, "the development of literacy skills in one language strongly predicts the acquisition of corresponding skills in another language later on" (Verhoeven, 1991: 72). It is generally accepted that in bilingual children, phonological awareness, word decoding, reading strategies, metacognitive awareness, and pragmatic awareness transfer from the L1 to the L2 (Chiappe, Siegal, & Gottardo, 2002; Geva, 2006; Lesaux et al., 2006; Wade-Woolley & Siegal, 1997). According to these studies, L2 reading skills are likely to represent a "amalgam of two systems in one mind,"

rather than being entirely different cognitively from L1 reading (Grabe, 2009: 145). Similar to this, Cook contends that rather than being totally separate systems, "since the first language and the other language or languages are in the same mind they must form a language super-system at some level" (2003: 2).

As a result, reading and understanding texts in a second language can be accomplished using skills from the first language. These studies, however, presuppose that for such transfer to be advantageous, there must be a certain level of ability or proficiency in the second language. It has not been thought of to transfer skills from the first language to enable proficiency in the second. This is probably due to the fact that first-generation learners have not been included in the research studies conducted thus far. One cannot assume that such children will always have access to print materials at home. Therefore, the level of proficiency between the two languages must be taken into account in such research.

Language threshold hypothesis

This idea has roots in Clarke's (1980) short-circuit hypothesis, which holds that "successful first-language readers fail to read well in the second language due to inadequate knowledge of the second language" (Alderson. 2000:38). It implies that before L2 reading skills could be transferred to help with reading, L2 learners needed to acquire sufficient L2 language proficiency. The well-known question posed by Alderson (1984): "Is second language reading a reading problem or a language problem" served to emphasize this point further. The Language Threshold Hypothesis was established as a result of his review. Additionally, Bernhardt (2005) noted that the threshold hypothesis sought to determine the function of transfer as a component of the development of L2 reading, i.e., what transfers and when does it transfer.

Consequently, the goal of this study is to "deal with varying levels of L2 capability (in this case, English), and more importantly, reading comprehension capability in the first language" (Tamil). In the student's mind, there are two systems. But they are unquestionably not isolated and separate. Although the systems may be at various stages of development, they complement and support one another to enable the student to understand what is read in either language. Consequently, the goal of this study is to "deal with varying levels of L2 capability (in this case, English), and more importantly, reading comprehension capability in the first language" (Tamil). In the student's mind, there are two systems. But they are unquestionably not isolated and separate. Although the systems may be at various stages of development, they complement and support one another to enable the student to understand what is read in either language. This implies that L2 readers have access to both L1 and L2. The interaction of two languages as part of L2 reading processes is known as "multi-competency" according to Cook (1992: 1997).

Effect of transfer on reading strategies

The majority of reading strategy studies have concentrated on students' strategic behavior in L1 and L2, and more specifically on how reading strategies are transferred from L1 to L2. Studies on the transfer of cross-language reading strategies among bilingual cohorts in American schools have been conducted. According to the findings, students are more likely to employ comparable reading L1 and L2 strategies (Pritchard. 1990). When readers believe that the two languages are similar, there is a significant decrease in the transfer of strategies (Garcia. 1991; Jimenez. Garcia. & Pearson. 1996). Additionally, practicing a strategy in one language reduces its use in the other (Muniz-Swicegood. 1994; Padron.1992).

All of these findings support the claim that strategies learned in one language are typically transferable to another when taken collectively. Interestingly, every participant in these studies was a bilingual speaker of two closely related languages. English and Spanish. As a result, the findings' generalizability has been called into question. Accordingly, a study by Hua (1997; cited in Koda 2005: 220) showed that bilingual readers using unrelated L1 and L2 also used the same comprehension strategies in both languages. As a result, it is once again confirmed that, regardless of linguistic distance, reading strategies as well as comprehension skills can be transferred between languages, with or without the aid of instruction. The characteristics of transferrable tactics changes based on the students' or learners' proficiency level and level. Only those studies that deal with this cohort in depth are examined since this study is focused on younger bilinguals with low proficiency levels.

We quickly review the research that has been done in this field. Compared to the strategies used by three successful monolingual English readers, it was discovered that Jimenez, Garcia, and Pearson (1996) reported on the strategies used by eight successful and three less successful Latina/o readers of English. All subjects ranged in age from 11 to 13; teacher evaluations served as the basis for determining "success." (b) Subjects' own evaluations; and (c) English reading proficiency test results. Both unprompted and prompted think-aloud were used to collect data. During interviews, questions about prior knowledge and passage recall are asked.

The findings of the study are as follows.

- Better L1 readers, whether in English or Tamil. used comparable reading techniques to try to understand.
- As expected, the successful EL1 (English as a first language) readers had a greater and more comprehensive vocabulary than the EL2 (English as a second language) readers.
- Twenty-two strategies, divided into three major categories (text-initiated, reader-initiated, and interactive), were discovered.
- Successful L2 readers applied particular cross-language techniques. specifically looking for and analyzing cognates. assessing understanding, rereading, and asking questions.

Successful L2 readers adopted a "unitary view of reading" (Jimenez et al. 1996: 99), in which students took advantage of their awareness of the parallels and discrepancies between languages while employing strategies to understand reading texts written in L2. Less proficient L2 readers, on the other hand, were more focused on getting the job done than on the quality of their comprehension. They failed to use problem-solving techniques and were unable to accept that skills learned for reading in one language could be applied to reading in another.

- Readers who were more proficient focused more on creating meaning in both languages.
- Students from all proficiency levels applied comprehension-problem-solving techniques from reading in Spanish (L1) to reading in English (L2).
- When it came to second language strategic reading, second language proficiency was less important than L1 strategy use.
 - Although there are similarities between the reading strategies used by students in L1 and L2 and the strategy groups they used, such as cognitive, compensatory, meta-cognitive, and social strategies, the proportions of the reading strategies they use vary.
 - Students have a limited understanding of and ability to use efficient reading comprehension strategies.

The results of these three sets of studies suggest that strategies can be transferred, but it is obvious that, as with all other strategy research, strategies do not automatically transfer without training. A language learner frequently employs strategies in a deliberate and conscious manner. In the case of language users, it may become automatic and develop into a skill with time and use. It appears that raising awareness is required for learners to transfer a strategy from one language to another. Background knowledge, the capacity to infer what is said, and lastly metalinguistic awareness are the areas of language where such strategies can be applied.

The study, which is primarily ethnographic in nature, necessitates a thorough comprehension of the school setting, the students, and the other stakeholders. Therefore, classes were observed casually and without drawing attention to ourselves. There were also casual conversations with the teachers and the kids. These discussions were conducted in Tamil as necessary. The majority of the children come from lower middle-class and low-income Tamil-speaking families. Outside of the English classroom, they hardly ever use English. The majority of the parents lack literacy. However, the mother of one child has completed her tenth-class school exams, while the father holds a graduate degree. The fathers all work as small fans, daily wage earners, teachers, carpenters, or paddy merchants or vendors, while all the mothers stay at home. Except for one, every child has a nuclear family. Despite the fact that the majority of the parents are illiterate, informal conversations with the parents revealed that they are very concerned about their children's education. The primary concern for the majority of parents and kids is providing for their daily needs of survival. Despite this, they believed that English was crucial for global financial and social mobility and were determined to do whatever it took for their children to learn the language, even at a young age.

- What do you do in your free time?
- Name some books/magazines you have read recently.
- How do your teachers teach reading in class?
- What are some of the activities/tasks/exercises used in the classroom"?

These kids don't have any English storybooks to read, and neither do their parents, who don't even subscribe to a newspaper. The textbook is frequently the only source of English information. Any child who feels the need to read English (in order to perform better academically in class) is forced to pick up that textbook and read it repeatedly. The slightly older kids, however, admitted that despite their desire to read, they did not find the "stories" to be particularly compelling.

Analyzing the aforementioned "reading-like" activities in the classroom critically reveals that neat copying is given priority. rather than practicing comprehension, rote learning, "choral reading," or "responsive reading" (teacher reads, students repeat) [Birch, 2007: 177J are used. Kids are doing useless things like memorizing facts by heart. "Rote" repetition refers to reading aloud without understanding (Williams 2011: 43-44). As far as cognitive engagement with the text is concerned, such activities do not count as reading and writing activities. Children are urged to read in our educational system "to get the words right" (reading for identification) (Smith, 2004:40) rather than reading for meaning, or to "make sense of what is being read." If there had been institutional support available. There was much more that could have been done. assuming that support and assistance will be accessible in the future and that such "understanding of the context" will be possible.

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